

Directional solidification of magnetostrictive Fe-Ga-Cr alloy

Masoud Rahbar-Niazi

Translation of the last three chapters of my master thesis Submitted to
Sahand University of Technology

Supervisors:

Prof. Syamak Hossein-Nedjad

Prof. Habib Badri-Ghavifekr

January 10, 2015

Abstract

Iron-gallium (Galfenol) alloys exhibit very high magnetostriction under low applied magnetic fields. These alloys can be used as sensor materials and mechanical actuators. Although single crystals of Galfenol exhibit higher magnetostriction, due to their high cost of production and poor mechanical properties, polycrystalline Galfenol alloys with a crystalline texture are preferred alternatives to single crystals. In the present study, the effect of rapid and directional solidification and cooling rate on the physical, mechanical and magnetic properties of polycrystalline Galfenol alloys was investigated. The phase field method was also used to simulate the evolution of magnetic domains in Galfenol alloys. For this purpose, a Galfenol alloy with a composition $Fe_{86.32}Ga_{11.31}Cr_{2.37}$ was prepared under Argon atmosphere protection through vacuum arc remelting (VAR) in a water-cooled Copper mold. A suction system was used to increase the solidification rate. To investigate the effect of heat treatment on magneto-striction, the cast sample was annealed at 258°C for 7 hrs and then quenched in water. Subsequently, the quenched sample was similarly annealed and then cooled in air. The microstructure of the samples was examined by optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and X-ray diffraction. Micro-hardness testing was used to evaluate the hardness of the samples. The Magneto-striction was measured by the Michelson interferometry method. The results showed that the cast sample has a structure with columnar grains in the direction of the thermal gradient (radial). Performing heat treatment reduces the magnet-striction. X-ray diffraction patterns indicated that all samples were single-phase and that a strong texture was present in the cast sample. The hardness values obtained were about 758 Vickers, which did not change with heat treatment. The simulation of the evolution of the magnetic domains using the phase-field micro-elasticity method showed that the phase field method is able to predict the arrangement of magnetic domains and the amount of magneto-striction in both single-crystalline and polycrystalline cases.

Keywords: Galfenol,directional solidification,rapid solidification,magneto-striction, phase field simulation

Contents

1	Materials and Methods	4
1.1	Experimental setup	4
1.1.1	Melting and casting of the sample	4
1.1.2	Preparation of samples for microstructural studies	7
1.1.3	Heat treatment	7
1.1.4	Design of a magnetic assembly	7
1.1.5	Determination of Average Chemical Composition	8
1.1.6	Microstructural Examination by Optical Microscopy	8
1.1.7	Microstructural Examination by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)	8
1.1.8	Phase Structure Analysis by X-ray Diffraction (XRD)	8
1.1.9	Hardness Measurement	9
1.1.10	Magnetostriction Measurement	9
2	Investigation of Microstructural, Magnetic, and Mechanical Properties of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy	12
2.1	Chemical Composition Analysis by EDS	12
2.2	Microstructure Analysis by Optical Microscopy	13
2.3	Characterization of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy by X-ray Diffraction	19
2.4	Hardness Testing of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy	24
2.5	Magnetostriction Measurement of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy	24
3	Phase Field Simulation of Magnetic Domains in Galfenol	27
3.0.1	Micromagnetic Model and Phase Field Micro-Elasticity	27
3.0.2	Numerical Calculations of the Phase Field	32

3.0.3	Fourier Transform and Discretization	33
3.0.4	Algorithm for Simulating Magnetic Domain Evolution in Single-Crystal Galfenol	34
3.0.5	Algorithm for Simulating Magnetic Domain Evolution in Polycrystalline Galfenol	35
3.1	Magnetic Domain Evolution and Magnetostrictive Behavior in Single-Crystal Galfenol Alloy	36
3.1.1	Magnetic Domain Evolution in the Absence of External Field	36
3.1.2	Magnetic Domain Evolution Under External Field	38
3.1.3	Domain Structure Dependence on Sample Size	40
3.1.4	Domain Structure Dependence on Magnetostriction Constant	41
3.1.5	Domain Structure Dependence on Magnetic Anisotropy Constant	42
4	Conclusions	47
5	Outlook	49
A	Phase Field Modeling Method	50
A.1	Local Free Energy Function	52
A.2	Elastic Free Energy	54
A.3	Numerical Methods for Phase Field Equations	55
B	Gauss-Seidel Projection Method for Micromagnetic Phenomena Simulation	56
C	Three-Dimensional Grain Growth Simulation	59

Chapter 1

Materials and Methods

This chapter describes the materials and equipment used in this research, as well as the parameters, coding algorithm, and numerical calculations for micromagnetic and microelastic simulations, both for the single-crystal and multi-crystal cases.

1.1 Experimental setup

1.1.1 Melting and casting of the sample

Using high purity (99.999%) Gallium and commercial pure iron and chromium, an alloy with the nominal composition $Fe_{86.32}Ga_{11.31}Cr_{2.37}$ (in weight percent) prepared by VAR (Figure 1.1 under the protection of argon atmosphere. For structural homogenization, the sample was remelted twice. The mold material is a water-cooled copper mold with water jets positioned around the mold (Figure 1.2). A vacuum pump is installed beneath the setup to draw the molten metal into the copper mold (see Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.1: VAR setup used for melting and directional solidification.

Figure 1.2: copper mold for rapid solidification

Figure 1.3: Schematic of the VAR setup

The chemical analysis of the pure Ga used in this project is shown in Table 1.1

Table 1.1: Chemical analysis of gallium metal used in this study (in weight percent).

Ga	Fe	In	Na+K	Sb	Ca
99.999	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0003

The sample obtained from the casting process is a cylindrical rod with a length of 5 cm and a diameter of 6 mm (see Figure 1.4). A disk-shaped protrusion is present on one side of the sample due to an excess amount of melt compared to the mold's volume. This protrusion was removed from the sample for subsequent analysis.

Figure 1.4: The sample obtained through the VAR process.

Figure 1.5: a) transverse, and b) longitudinal section.

1.1.2 Preparation of samples for microstructural studies

To study the microstructure, 1 cm high discs were cut from the cylindrical sample after heat treatment using a wire-cut machine. The sample was then further sectioned into two parts along its thickness. One part was used to examine the cross-sectional area of the cylinder (transverse section), while the other part was used to analyze the microstructure along the cylinder axis (longitudinal section)(Figure 1.5).

1.1.3 Heat treatment

The prepared casting sample, after performing the magnetostriction test, was first annealed for 2 hours at 850 °C and then quenched in water. After determining the magnetostriction strain, the quenched sample was annealed for 2 hours at 850 °C and then cooled in air.

1.1.4 Design of a magnetic assembly

To generate a magnetic field, a solenoid with an inner diameter of 3 cm and a length of 15 cm was designed. To apply the magnetic field, 1538 turns of enameled copper wire with a diameter of 0.2 mm were used to create a field. A maximum of 2 amperes Direct current (DC) was applied to create the field. To calculate the magnetic field intensity at the center of the tubular wire and assuming that the field was uniform along the

length of the tubular wire, the following equation was used:

$$H = \frac{ni}{L} \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{L^* + D^*}} \right) \quad (1.1)$$

n is the number of coil turns, i is the current in amperes, L is the length of the coil in meters, D is the diameter of the coil in meters, and H is the field strength in amperes per meter.

1.1.5 Determination of Average Chemical Composition

To determine the chemical composition and the distribution of different elements in the sample, the EDS method was used. For greater accuracy, the chemical composition was analyzed at several distinct points, and the averages were reported.

1.1.6 Microstructural Examination by Optical Microscopy

To perform metallography, the samples were sanded up to 5000 grit sandpaper and then mechanically polished. To etch the samples, a 5% solution of Nital was used.

1.1.7 Microstructural Examination by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The microstructure of cast and heat-treated samples was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with a Cam Scan Vega Tescsn MV2200 model. The samples were prepared by final polishing before imaging.

1.1.8 Phase Structure Analysis by X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

To characterize the phase structures of the cast and heat-treated samples, XRD was performed using a Burker Advance D8 device (equipped with a $\text{Cu}(K_\alpha)$ target with a wavelength of 1.5406 Å). The device operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. A nickel filter was used, and the scanning parameters are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Conditions for XRD scanning in this research.

2θ (°)	Step size (°)	Count time (s)	Total scan time (min)
40–90	0.02	1	41

1.1.9 Hardness Measurement

Galfenol samples in cast and heat-treated conditions were subjected to hardness testing. Hardness testing was performed on the transverse and longitudinal cross-sections at several points, and their averages were reported. The discs prepared for metallography were polished and prepared for the hardness test. To minimize errors, the mounted samples were ensured to have parallel top and bottom surfaces and were polished to a smooth finish.

The hardness tests were conducted using a Zwick/Roell Z2.5 microhardness tester, with an applied load of 100 grams and a dwell time of 10 seconds.

1.1.10 Magnetostriction Measurement

In this study, a Michelson interferometer was used to measure magnetostriction strain (Figure 1.6). The schematic of the Michelson interferometry is shown in Figure 1.7a. In a Michelson interferometer, the laser beam is split into two beams by a beam splitter. Each of these beams is reflected by a mirror and interferes on a screen behind the beam splitter (Figure 1.7b).

Figure 1.6: Setup for the measurement of magnetostriction strain using Michelson interferometer

Figure 1.7: a) Schematic of Michelson interferometry setup for measuring magnetostriction strain, b) The interference pattern appearing on the screen

To measure magnetostriction, one of the mirrors was attached to the sample placed inside the magnetic field. The other mirror is positioned at an angle such that interferences in the form of bright and dark concentric circles are visible on the screen (Figure 1.7b). Bright circles are created when the difference in the path traveled by the reflected laser is a multiple of 2π . To converge the incoming laser from the source to the beam splitter, two lenses were used, with a factor of +5 and +100 mm, and a -100 mm lens was used to observe the interference patterns on the screen. The other side of the sample was threaded to a steel cylinder. To ensure the cylinder remained stationary, it was welded to a steel rod, which was securely fixed onto a wooden base using two screws.

A solenoid is used to generate a magnetic field, causing the sample to change length, causing the mirror 2 attached to the sample to move forward. As the mirror 2 moves forward by half the wavelength of the laser, the diameter of the central circle is reduced and eliminated. The change in length is calculated by counting the number of eliminated circles and using the following equation:

$$\Delta l = n \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad (1.2)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the laser, and n is the number of interference fringes eliminated by the applied current. The amount of strain is calculated by dividing the

change in length by the initial length of the sample. The laser used in this research is of type HeNe with a wavelength of 632 nm. The accuracy of the device measurement was verified using a pure iron sample.

Chapter 2

Investigation of Microstructural, Magnetic, and Mechanical Properties of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy

This chapter presents the results of microstructural characterization for both as-cast and heat-treated samples using optical microscopy. The samples were then characterized by X-ray diffraction to analyze their crystal texture. Subsequent analysis includes scanning electron microscopy observations, microhardness measurements, and finally the obtained magnetostriction curves.

2.1 Chemical Composition Analysis by EDS

Figure 2.1 shows the elemental analysis results for the iron-gallium alloy used in this study. As observed, the sample is free of any harmful compounds including carbides and oxides. Due to gallium's high vapor pressure, approximately 3% of it was lost during the casting process.

Figure 2.1: Chemical composition of the as-cast sample obtained by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS).

2.2 Microstructure Analysis by Optical Microscopy

Figure 2.2 shows the optical microstructure of the as-cast sample's cross-section at different magnifications. As observed, the produced sample exhibits a completely single-phase structure. Some irregularly shaped dark inclusions are also present in the microstructure (indicated by arrows in the figure), likely formed during the casting process.

The grain structure consists of fine grains near the mold-melt interface region, which transition to larger equiaxed grains toward the sample center as the cooling rate decreases. Figure 2.3 demonstrates the presence and orientation of dendrites in various directions within the central regions of the cast sample's cross-section.

Key observations:

- Dendrite arm spacing increases farther from the mold surface
- Dendrite cores become thicker with decreasing cooling rate
- Near-surface regions (higher cooling rates) show:

Figure 2.2: Cross-sectional microstructure of the as-cast sample at different magnifications, a) $\times 50$, b) $\times 100$, c) $\times 200$

- Finer dendrites
- Smaller secondary dendrite arm spacing
- Temperature gradient below critical value for equilibrium solidification
- Stronger constitutional undercooling

The available time for solute element redistribution decreases at higher cooling rates, consequently requiring smaller secondary dendrite arm spacing to prevent constitutional undercooling.

Figures 2.4, 2.6 show the microstructure of the samples annealed-quenched in wan-

Figure 2.3: Dendritic structure of the central region of the as-cast sample. Top section of the figure is closer to the center of the sample.

Figure 2.4: Microstructure of the annealed-quenched sample.

ter and annealed-air cooled respectively. Both samples exhibit similar single-phase structures. The copper mold used in this study provides strong radial thermal gradients, resulting in solidification characteristics where:

- Solidification initiates equiaxially from the cylindrical wall surface
- Progresses inward following typical casting patterns
- Microstructural evolution depends on:
 - Cooling medium (water vs air)
 - Resultant thermal gradients
 - Solute redistribution effects

Gradually, the grains grow columnar along the thermal gradient toward the sample center, ultimately appearing as fine equiaxed grains in the central region. The presence of fine equiaxed grains in the center results from constitutional undercooling in the alloy. When the solid-liquid interfaces meet at the ingot center, their constitutional undercooling zones eventually overlap. At this stage, significant undercooling develops in the melt near the ingot center. As the columnar zone grows, the concentration of solute atoms in the melt ahead of the solid-liquid interface increases. Consequently, to sustain solidification, the interface temperature must continuously decrease. As the two interfaces approach each other, the temperature at the ingot center converges with the interface temperature, causing the temperature-distance curve in the melt to become linear. The central equiaxed zone confirms that constitutional undercooling has occurred in this region, reaching sufficient magnitude to enable nucleation within the central melt.

The as-cast sample exhibits a nearly equiaxed grain structure, contrasting with the heat-treated samples where large columnar grains are absent. Note that:

- The as-cast metallographic sample was taken from the upper cylinder section
- Heat-treated samples were sectioned from the cylinder's middle region
- Structural differences originate from spatial variations rather than heat treatment effects

Figure 2.5: Microstructure of the annealed-air cooled sample.

Key microstructural observations:

- Dendritic structures vanish after heat treatment due to:
 - Compositional homogenization
 - Dissolution of solute-rich microsegregations
- Shorter dendrite arm spacing requires less annealing time for complete homogenization

Figure ?? reveals a clearly visible central pore in the polished cross-section. These macroscopic cavities form due to:

- Extremely rapid cooling rates (exceeding 200 K/s)
- Insufficient liquid metal feeding during solidification
- Volumetric shrinkage effects in the final freezing regions

The cooling rate is so high that the liquid metal lacks sufficient time for feeding during solidification. These cavities significantly degrade the material's mechanical properties. However, since most magnetostrictive applications use hollow cylindrical

Figure 2.6: The central pore seen from the a) cross-sectional b) lateral views of the polished annealed-air cooled sample.

configurations, the central region containing these defects can be removed by machining.

Figure 2.7 shows the microstructure of the annealed-air-cooled sample in the central regions of the longitudinal section at two different magnifications. As could be predicted, the grains adjacent to the mold surface grew columnar and gradually transformed into equiaxed grains. As we get closer to the center of the sample, the size of the equiaxed grains becomes smaller. The interaction between secondary phases and grain boundaries is shown by arrows. Impurity atoms of the inclusion or secondary particle type can inhibit grain growth in metals. As can be seen from the figure, the upper boundary of the two boundaries indicated by arrows is moving upward and the lower boundary is moving downward, with secondary particles preventing their movement. As the length of columnar grains increases, their diameter also increases, which results from the elimination of crystals with less favorable orientations. Increasing temperature reduces the retarding effect of secondary phases.

The presence of columnar grains perpendicular to the magnetic field direction is undesirable because with this arrangement, more grain boundaries are created against the applied magnetic field, acting as barriers to the movement of magnetic domain walls. Grain boundaries are low-energy sites for magnetic domain nucleation. On the other hand, since the orientation of adjacent grains differs from each other, the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy makes the movement of magnetic domain walls more difficult. It is better for the applied magnetic field direction to be parallel to the

Figure 2.7: Longitudinal section of the central regions at magnifications a) $\times 50$ b) $\times 200$.

growth direction of columnar grains.

2.3 Characterization of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy by X-ray Diffraction

Figure 2.8 shows the XRD patterns of as-cast, annealed-quenched, and annealed-air-cooled samples from the cylindrical cross-section. The characteristic (200), (100), and (211) peaks indicate a body-centered cubic (BCC) α -iron phase structure. Substituting iron atoms with gallium atoms shifts the peak positions corresponding to pure α -iron

BCC phase to smaller 2θ angles. Therefore, adding gallium causes lattice expansion. No weak reflections corresponding to ordered DO₃ or B2 phases were observed, confirming the high solidification rate prevented their formation.

The similar crystal structures of ordered DO₃ and α -iron may cause peak overlap. Detailed examination of the (200) and (211) peaks (Figure 2.9) shows only $K\alpha_1$ - $K\alpha_2$ splitting - completely resolved in as-cast samples but overlapping in heat-treated samples. This may result from structural defects in these samples. The parameters obtained from Racherger refinement of the diffraction patterns for as-cast, quenched, and air-cooled samples are shown in Tables 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 respectively. The refinement was performed using X'Pert HighScore Plus software.

Table 2.1: Parameters obtained from Racherger refinement of diffraction patterns for as-cast sample.

2θ	d-spacing (Å)	Peak height	Peak area	FWHM
44/4314	2/02222	1843/35	207/84290	0/19200
64/5516	1/44252	117/5	39/48087	0/16800
81/6863	1/17784	366/49	87/95850	0/12000

Table 2.2: Parameters obtained from Racherger refinement of diffraction patterns for quenched sample.

2θ	d-spacing (Å)	Peak height	Peak area	FWHM
44/3935	2/02897	229/3	105/42270	0/3149
64/7822	1/43794	15/42	12/57523	0/55100
81/6413	1/17838	27/35	26/25553	0/48000

Table 2.3: Parameters obtained from Racherger refinement of diffraction patterns for air-cooled sample.

2θ	d-spacing (Å)	Peak height	Peak area	FWHM
44/3855	2/02932	296/63	43/49	0/0984
64/3458	1/44664	19/35	15/69881	0/5492
81/5387	1/17960	33/36	43/49010	0/67200

This approach eliminates the influence of the $K\alpha_2$ peak when calculating peak width. Based on the FWHM values, we conclude that annealing followed by water quenching introduces residual stresses due to differential cooling rates across the sample, resulting in wider diffraction peak profiles.

Re-annealing followed by air cooling shows sharper peaks compared to the quenched sample due to partial release of residual stresses, though this heat treatment remains

Figure 2.8: X-ray diffraction pattern from cross-section of the a) as-cast, b) annealed-quenched, and c) annealed-air cooled

Figure 2.9: Diffraction peak (200) (left) and (211) (right) for as-cast (top), quenched (middle), and air-cooled (bottom) samples.

insufficient for complete stress relief. The relative intensity changes of peaks in Tables 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 indicate texture development, where the intensity ratio of (200)/(211) is 0.36 in as-cast, 0.54 in annealed-quenched, and 0.66 in annealed-air-cooled samples. This is due to the different regions from which the sample was cut as these heat treatments cannot impose significant texture due to mechanisms such as recrystallization. The [100] texture is particularly desirable for magnetostrictive applications, as single-crystal studies of Galfenol alloys demonstrate superior magnetostriction along this orientation.

The longitudinal XRD pattern (Figure 2.10) shows identical BCC peaks as the transverse section but with similar peak broadening in heat-treated samples and dramatic intensity variations, especially in as-cast where the (211) peak shows very high intensity while (200) and (110) peaks have negligible intensity, indicating strong crystallographic texture. Although texture modification in Fe-Ga alloys through grain growth, recrystallization, and surface energy reduction has been reported by many researchers [8,37,52,56,62-64], the extreme intensity differences observed here likely stem from taking XRD patterns from different sample regions (columnar vs. equiaxed zones). Quantitative texture analysis would require pole figures or ODF measurements.

Figure 2.10: X-ray diffraction pattern from longitudinal section of the a) as-cast, b) annealed-quenched, and c) annealed-air cooled.

Figure 2.11: Vickers hardness test of as-cast (left), annealed-quenched (middle), and annealed-air cooled (right).

2.4 Hardness Testing of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy

Figure 2.11 shows the Vickers hardness values of the iron-gallium-chromium alloy in different processing conditions: as-cast, water-quenched, and air-cooled. As observed, no significant change in hardness values is seen between different processing states, indicating that no specific phase transformations or precipitation hardening occurred during heat treatment.

The reported Vickers hardness values for binary Galfenol alloys with gallium content between 15 to 20 percent range from 200 to 250. For gallium contents above 30 percent, the hardness exceeds 475 Vickers [65]. The hardness obtained in this study is approximately 250 Vickers, which given the low gallium content demonstrates high strengthening effect of chromium [25].

2.5 Magnetostriction Measurement of Iron-Gallium-Chromium Alloy

The magnetostriction curves as a function of applied magnetic field for as-cast, quenched, and air-cooled conditions are shown in Figures 2.12, 2.13, and 2.14 respectively. The

general shape of the curves is similar: a small magnetostriction increase at lower fields (due to 180° domain wall motion), followed by a steeper increase (from 90° domain wall motion), and finally saturation. The applied field required for magnetic saturation is approximately equal in all three samples. The highest magnetostriction value of 57.9 ppm was observed in the as-cast sample under an applied field of 25 kA/m. The saturation magnetostriction decreases to 37.9 ppm in the quenched sample. The lowest magnetostriction value of 31.6 ppm was measured in the air-cooled sample.

Figure 2.12: magnetostriction curves as a function of applied magnetic field for as-cast sample.

Figure 2.13: magnetostriction curves as a function of applied magnetic field for annealed-quenched sample.

Figure 2.14: magnetostriction curves as a function of applied magnetic field for annealed-air cooled sample.

The precise origin of magnetostriction in Gallenol alloys remains unclear. One theory suggests the high magnetostriction in iron-gallium alloys results from Ga atom pairing in the DO_3 structure. Band structure calculations [50] show the $B2$ structure enhances while the DO_3 structure reduces magnetostriction.

The detrimental effect of DO_3 is well-established since short-range ordered DO_3 domains (SRO) dramatically decrease magnetostriction. However, small SRO regions of DO_3 that form at low Ga concentrations have negligible impact. Studies also reveal different heat treatments produce SRO domains of varying sizes. Faster cooling rates form smaller SRO domains. This is particularly true for alloys containing less than %15 atomic percent gallium. At concentrations above %19, there is a low probability of significant gallium atom pairing occurring during heat treatment.

Slowly-cooled samples allow Ga atoms sufficient time and thermal energy to separate and form long-range ordered structures like DO_3 . In rapidly-quenched samples, high-temperature disorder becomes frozen, preserving Ga pairs down to room temperature.

The pseudo-binary phase diagram indicates the $B2$ structure becomes more probable at elevated temperatures. However, recent simulations [51] reveal the alloys' high magnetostriction originates from electronic structure properties rather than precipitate formation. Furthermore, calculations demonstrate that substituting elements like Cu and Zn (with different electron counts than Ga) could enhance magnetostriction [51].

Chapter 3

Phase Field Simulation of Magnetic Domains in Galfenol

In this chapter, we discuss the simulation results of magnetic domain evolution and magnetostrictive behavior in a binary Galfenol alloy $\text{Fe}_{81.2}\text{Ga}_{18.7}$ for both single-crystal and polycrystalline states.

3.0.1 Micromagnetic Model and Phase Field Micro-Elasticity

In a micromagnetic model, the magnetic domain structure is described by the spatial distribution of local magnetization $\mathbf{M}(t)$. The temporal evolution of the magnetization arrangement, and consequently the domain structure, is governed by the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation:

$$(1 + \alpha^2) \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial t} = -\gamma \mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} - \frac{\gamma \alpha}{M_s} \mathbf{M} \times (\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) \quad (3.1)$$

where M_s is the saturation magnetization, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, α is the damping constant, and \mathbf{H}_{eff} is the effective magnetic field, which can be expressed as the variational derivative of the total free energy of the system with respect to magnetization:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = -\frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{\partial E}{\partial \mathbf{M}} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, μ_0 is the vacuum permeability. The total free energy of magnetostrictive materials is given by:

$$E = E_{\text{anis}} + E_{\text{exch}} + E_{\text{ms}} + E_{\text{external}} + E_{\text{elastic}} \quad (3.3)$$

where E_{anis} , E_{exch} , E_{ms} , E_{external} , and E_{elastic} represent the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy, exchange energy, magnetostatic energy, external field energy, and elastic energy, respectively.

The magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy for a cubic crystal is given by:

$$E_{\text{anis}} = \int [K_1(m_1^2m_2^2 + m_2^2m_3^2 + m_3^2m_1^2) + K_2m_1^2m_2^2m_3^2] dv \quad (3.4)$$

where m_i are the components of the magnetization unit vector, and K_1 and K_2 are the anisotropy constants.

The exchange energy is determined solely by the spatial variations of the magnetization orientation. The exchange energy is given by:

$$E_{\text{exch}} = A \int \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 m_{i,j}^2 \right) dv \quad (3.5)$$

where A is called the exchange stiffness constant. In this research, the comma in subscripts denotes spatial derivatives, for example:

$$\frac{\partial m_i}{\partial x_j} = m_{i,j} \quad (3.6)$$

where x_j represents the j -th component of the spatial vector in Cartesian coordinates.

The magnetostatic energy of a system can be expressed by:

$$E_{\text{ms}} = -\frac{1}{2}\mu_0M_s \int \mathbf{H}_d \cdot \mathbf{m} dv \quad (3.7)$$

where \mathbf{H}_d is the demagnetizing field determined by long-range interactions between magnetic moments. The demagnetizing field satisfies:

$$H_{d1,1} + H_{d2,2} + H_{d3,3} = -M_s(m_{1,1} + m_{2,2} + m_{3,3}) \quad (3.8)$$

where H_{di} are the components of \mathbf{H}_d . By introducing the scalar magnetic potential ϕ , we have:

$$H_{di} = -\phi_{,i} \quad (3.9)$$

Therefore, equation 3.8 can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta\phi = M_s(m_{1,1} + m_{2,2} + m_{3,3}) \quad (3.10)$$

The solution to the potential in equation 3.10 in Fourier space is given by:

$$\phi(\xi) = -i \frac{M_s[m_1(\xi)\xi_1 + m_2(\xi)\xi_2 + m_3(\xi)\xi_3]}{\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 + \xi_3^2} \quad (3.11)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and ξ_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) are the coordinate axes in Fourier space, and $\phi(\xi)$ and $\mathbf{m}(\xi)$ are the Fourier transforms of ϕ and \mathbf{m} , respectively. The value of ϕ in real space is obtained through the inverse Fourier transform of $\phi(\xi)$. Then \mathbf{H}_d can be calculated using equation 3.9.

The origin of Fourier space coordinates $\xi = (0, 0, 0)$ is a singular point in equation 3.11, and its effect arises from the demagnetizing field due to the average magnetization. That is, the magnetization at any point is the sum of homogeneous and inhomogeneous magnetization:

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}) = \overline{\mathbf{M}} + \delta\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3.12)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{M}}$ is the position-independent average magnetization and $\delta\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r})$ is the position-dependent inhomogeneous part. The average field is defined such that $\int \delta\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{v} = 0$. Therefore, to account for the demagnetizing field due to the average field, the demagnetizing field is written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_d(\overline{\mathbf{M}}) = \mathbf{N}\overline{\mathbf{M}} \quad (3.13)$$

where \mathbf{N} is the demagnetizing factor tensor whose value must be calculated for each specific shape. Thus, at each point we have

$$\mathbf{H}_d = \mathbf{H}_d(\overline{\mathbf{M}}) + \mathbf{H}_d(\delta\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}))$$

The effect of an external magnetic field $\mathbf{H}_{\text{external}}$ on the system's energy can be

analyzed through its interaction with the magnetization:

$$E_{\text{external}} = -\mu_0 M_s \int \mathbf{H}_{\text{external}} \cdot \mathbf{m} dv \quad (3.14)$$

For a cubic material with magnetostrictive properties, the deformation associated with local magnetization is described by the stress-free strain:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^0 = \begin{cases} \frac{3}{2} \lambda_{100} (m_i^2 - \frac{1}{3}) & i = j \\ \frac{3}{2} \lambda_{111} m_i m_j & i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

where λ_{100} and λ_{111} are the magnetostrictive constants for a cubic crystal.

To incorporate the effects of local deformations due to magnetostriction in magnetic domain structures, the elastic strain e_{ij} and consequently the elastic energy E_{elastic} are defined as:

$$e_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ij}^0 \quad (3.16)$$

where ε_{ij} is the total strain. The resulting elastic energy can be expressed as:

$$E_{\text{elastic}} = \frac{1}{2} \int C_{ijkl} e_{ij} e_{kl} dv = \frac{1}{2} \int C_{ijkl} (\varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ij}^0) (\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^0) dv \quad (3.17)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the elastic stiffness tensor. In these equations, the Einstein summation convention over repeated indices is used.

Following Khachatryan's theory, the total strain ε_{ij} can be expressed as the sum of homogeneous and heterogeneous strains:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) = \overline{\varepsilon_{ij}} + \eta_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3.18)$$

The homogeneous strain is defined such that:

$$\int \eta_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) dv = 0 \quad (3.19)$$

The homogeneous strain represents the macroscopic deformation caused by the domain structure, while the heterogeneous strain does not alter the macroscopic shape of the system.

The homogeneous equilibrium strain must satisfy the mechanical equilibrium con-

dition:

$$\sigma_{ij,j} = 0 \quad (3.20)$$

where σ_{ij} are the stress components given by:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}e_{kl} = C_{ijkl}(\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^0) \quad (3.21)$$

The equilibrium equation can be solved in Fourier space. First, we introduce a set of displacement fields u_i such that:

$$\eta_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad (3.22)$$

Thus, the equilibrium relations can be rewritten as:

$$C_{ijkl}u_{k,lj} = C_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl,j}^0 \quad (3.23)$$

The general solution for the displacement field in Fourier space is given by:

The general solution for the displacement field in Fourier space is expressed by:

$$u_i(\xi) = \frac{X_j N_{ij}(\xi)}{D(\xi)} \quad (3.24)$$

where:

- $\varepsilon_{kl}(\xi)$ and $u_i(\xi)$ are the Fourier transforms of $\varepsilon_{kl}(\mathbf{r})$ and $u_i(\mathbf{r})$
- $X_i = -iC_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl}^0(\xi)\xi_j$

For cubic materials, $D(\xi)$ and $N_{ij}(\xi)$ are defined as:

$$D(\xi) = \mu^2(\lambda + 2\mu + \chi)\xi^4 \quad (3.25)$$

$$+ \mu\chi(3\lambda + 2\mu + \chi)\xi^2(\xi_1^2\xi_2^2 + \xi_1^2\xi_3^2 + \xi_2^2\xi_3^2) \quad (3.26)$$

$$+ \chi^2(3\lambda + 2\mu + \chi)\xi_1^2\xi_2^2\xi_3^2 \quad (3.27)$$

$$N_{11}(\xi) = \mu^2\xi^4 + \mu(\lambda + \mu + \chi)\xi^2(\xi_2^2 + \xi_3^2) + \chi(3\lambda + 2\mu + \chi)\xi_2^2\xi_3^2 \quad (3.28)$$

The other components can be obtained by cyclic permutation of indices (1, 2, 3), where:

$$\lambda = C_{12}, \quad \mu = C_{44}, \quad \chi = C_{11} - C_{12} - 2C_{44}, \quad \xi^2 = \xi_i \xi_i \quad (3.29)$$

The displacement field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r})$ in real space can be obtained through the inverse Fourier transform of $\mathbf{u}(\xi)$. The heterogeneous strain can then be calculated using:

$$\eta_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3.30)$$

By minimizing the elastic energy with respect to homogeneous strain:

$$\frac{\partial E_{\text{elastic}}}{\partial \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}} = 0 = V C_{ijkl} \bar{\epsilon}_{kl} - C_{ijkl} \int \epsilon_{kl} dv \quad (3.31)$$

we obtain the average strain:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{kl} = \frac{1}{V} \int \epsilon_{kl} dv \quad (3.32)$$

Using the stress-free strain from equation 3.15, the compatible strain can be expressed as:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{3}{2} \lambda_{100} (\langle m_i m_j \rangle - \frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij}) & i = j \\ \frac{3}{2} \lambda_{111} \langle m_i m_j \rangle & i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (3.33)$$

where λ_{100} and λ_{111} are magnetostrictive constants, and the volume average $\langle m_i m_j \rangle$ over the system includes the domain structure.

3.0.2 Numerical Calculations of the Phase Field

For simulating the evolution of magnetic domains we investigate the alloy composition $\text{Fe}_{81.3}\text{Ga}_{18.7}$ with the parameters given in Table 1-5. To solve the numerical phase field equations, the Gauss-Seidel projection method described in the appendix is used. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in all three directions, x_1, x_2, x_3 . The magnitude of magnetization in each element is normalized, meaning $M_S = \sqrt{M^x{}^2 + M^y{}^2 + M^z{}^2}$. However, M can vary in all three directions. For the damping factor, $\alpha = 0.05$, is used. Dimensionless parameters $A^* = 0.0625$ and $\Delta\tau = 0.1$ are considered for exchange

stiffness and time step size. It is assumed that no mechanical force is applied to the sample.

Table 3.1: Magnetic and elastic constants of the Fe_{81.3}Ga_{18.7} alloy [?]

Magnetic Saturation	Magnetic Stress Constants	Elastic Constants	Magnetic Anisotropy
$M_S = 1.443 \times 10^6$ A/m	$\lambda_{1,100} = 2.64 \times 10^{-4}$	$c_{11} = 1.96 \times 10^{11}$ N/m ²	$K_1 = 2 \times 10^4$ j/m ³
	$\lambda_{1,111} = -4.05 \times 10^{-4}$	$c_{12} = 1.23 \times 10^{11}$ N/m ²	$K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4$ j/m ³
		$c_{44} = 1.23 \times 10^{11}$ N/m ²	

3.0.3 Fourier Transform and Discretization

If a domain (Ω) with dimensions $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ is considered, discretized by elements of size $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$ in the three directions x, y, z respectively, then there will be N_x, N_y, N_z nodes in the mentioned three directions. Thus, each node in the domain is specified by integers such as (i, j, k) in three dimensions. The (discrete) Fourier transform of a function is defined as follows, where r is the real-space (direct) vector in Cartesian coordinates:

$$F(H(r)) = H(g) = \sum_{\Omega} H(r) \exp(-2\pi j g' \cdot r) dr = \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \sum_{j=1}^{N_y} \sum_{k=1}^{N_z} H(r) \exp(-j g \cdot r) dr \quad (3.34)$$

where g' is the Fourier-space (reciprocal) vector, $j = \sqrt{-1}$, and $g = 2\pi g'$.

The inverse of a function is defined as follows:

$$F^{-1}(H(g)) = H(r) = \sum_{\Omega} H(g) \exp(2\pi j g' \cdot r) dg = \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \sum_{j=1}^{N_y} \sum_{k=1}^{N_z} H(g) \exp(j g \cdot r) dg \quad (3.35)$$

$g = n_1 g_1 + n_2 g_2 + n_3 g_3$ where n_i is an integer and g_i represents the reciprocal space vector. The unit vectors in Fourier space are given as follows:

$$g_1 = 2\pi \frac{L_y \hat{y} \times L_z \hat{z}}{L_x \hat{x} \cdot L_y \hat{y} \times L_z \hat{z}}, g_2 = 2\pi \frac{L_z \hat{z} \times L_x \hat{x}}{L_x \hat{x} \cdot L_y \hat{y} \times L_z \hat{z}}, g_3 = 2\pi \frac{L_x \hat{x} \times L_y \hat{y}}{L_x \hat{x} \cdot L_y \hat{y} \times L_z \hat{z}} \quad (3.36)$$

In the present study, the IFFT and FFT commands in MATLAB were used to com-

pute the Fourier transform and inverse Fourier transform, respectively.

3.0.4 Algorithm for Simulating Magnetic Domain Evolution in Single-Crystal Galfenol

For simulating magnetic domains in Galfenol alloy, the following algorithm was used:

1. After discretizing the system into a $40 \times 40 \times 40$ grid of nodes and defining Fourier space vectors using Equations 3.36, each node was assigned a unit magnetic moment vector (\mathbf{m}) with random orientation, and their three-dimensional Fourier transform was computed.

2. The stress-free strain was calculated using Equation 3.15, and its Fourier transform was taken. The displacement in Fourier space was determined from Equation 3.24, and its real-space counterpart was obtained via inverse Fourier transform. The resulting displacement values were then substituted into Equation 3.30 to compute the heterogeneous strain. After computing the average magnetization values, the homogeneous strain is obtained from Equation 3.33. The variations in elastic energy with respect to magnetic moments are calculated by differentiating Equation 3.17.

3. The changes in magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy with respect to magnetic moments at each point are calculated by differentiating Equation 3.4.

4. Using Equation 3.11, the potential function in Fourier space is computed, and its inverse Fourier transform is taken. Substituting this into Equation 3.9, the demagnetizing field at each point (node) is obtained. The demagnetizing field from the average field is calculated using Equation 3.13. The value of N is set as a vector (1000). By summing the demagnetizing field and the field from the average magnetization, the total demagnetizing field is computed, and then the variations in magnetostatic energy are obtained by differentiating Equation 3.7.

5. A constant external magnetic field is applied, and its effect on the system energy is calculated by differentiating Equation 3.14.

6. The temporal evolution of magnetic moments is computed using the Gauss-Seidel method described in the Appendix.

7. Steps 2 through 6 are repeated for successive time intervals to simulate the time evolution.

Throughout all calculations, spatial derivatives were evaluated using the forward

Figure 3.1: Grain structure simulated by phase field modeling

finite difference method.

3.0.5 Algorithm for Simulating Magnetic Domain Evolution in Polycrystalline Galfenol

The simulation of magnetic domain evolution in polycrystalline Galfenol begins with generating a grain structure using a discrete phase-field method described in Appendix A (Figure ??). In the current study, the grains are assumed to be static and remain unchanged over time. The simulated polycrystal consists of 23 grains, where each grain is assumed to have a distinct crystallographic orientation different from its neighbors.

To solve the elasticity and magnetism equations, a global coordinate system was used for all grains. The orientation of each grain is described by three Euler angles (ϕ , θ , ψ). The transformation matrix from global to local coordinates is defined as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \phi \cos \psi - \cos \theta \sin \phi \sin \psi & -\cos \phi \sin \psi - \cos \theta \sin \phi \cos \psi & \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ \sin \phi \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi & -\sin \phi \sin \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi & \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ \sin \theta \sin \psi & \sin \theta \cos \psi & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.37)$$

The magnetic moment vector in local coordinates (\mathbf{m}^L) is related to the magnetic moment in global coordinates (\mathbf{m}) through the transformation:

$$m_i^L = R_{ij}m_j \quad (3.38)$$

where R_{ij} are components of the rotation matrix (3.37). The stress-free strain and magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy were calculated using the local coordinate magnetic moment \mathbf{m}^L , while other energy terms were computed using the global coordinate magnetic moment \mathbf{m} .

3.1 Magnetic Domain Evolution and Magnetostrictive Behavior in Single-Crystal Galfenol Alloy

3.1.1 Magnetic Domain Evolution in the Absence of External Field

Figure 3.2 shows the temporal evolution of magnetic domains. In these calculations each time step is 0.2 ns. The simulated samples were examined with $40 \times 40 \times 4$ elements having a cell size of 6 nm in all three directions, resulting in total sample dimensions of 240×240 nm - effectively representing a thin film.

The images in this figure display magnetization vector arrangements with components m_1 and m_2 , where shorter vector lengths indicate orientations nearly perpendicular to the page (with larger third components m_3). Note all images correspond to the $x_3 = 1$ surface, meaning they are two-dimensional representations.

Figure 3.2: Magnetic domain temporal evolution in the absence of applied field in simulation steps of a)1, b) 6, c) 10, d) 15, and e) 20.

For the iron-gallium alloy with our target composition, the first anisotropy constant K_1 is positive and the second anisotropy constant K_2 equals $K_2 = -\frac{9}{4}K_1$ making the $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions the easy magnetic axes. In this system, domain structures are primarily determined by the competition between:

- Domain wall energy (exchange energy)
- Demagnetization energy
- Elastic energy

Although the sample dimensions are small, showing some differences compared to bulk ferromagnetic materials, the simulated sample is large enough to form multiple domains. As shown, the initial random configuration evolves into magnetic domains with orientations determined by magnetic anisotropy energy. All six easy magnetic axes are nearly equally represented.

The domains are separated by 90° and 180° domain walls. 90° walls are aligned along the $[010]$ directions, which represent the average magnetic orientation.

3.1.2 Magnetic Domain Evolution Under External Field

When a ferromagnetic material is subjected to an external field, its magnetic domain configuration transitions to a new equilibrium state. The phase field model can successfully simulate this dynamic process.

Figure 3.3 shows the domain evolution under an external magnetic field of 1 kA/m applied along the positive x_1 direction. The initial magnetization state exhibits sharp domain walls. With field application, magnetization vectors near domain walls first reorient to align with the external field direction. The domain walls transition from sharp to Bloch-type (diffuse), while regions opposing the field gradually diminish and field-parallel regions grow, ultimately yielding a single-domain structure aligned with the applied field. Under these conditions, the thin film exhibits positive strain along x_1 and negative strain along the two transverse directions.

Figure 3.3: Magnetic domain temporal evolution under the external applied field in simulation steps of a) 1, b) 6, c) 10, d) 15, and e) 20.

The magnetostrictive response of a material depends directly on domain evolution under an external field. Maximum magnetostriction occurs when achieving an ideal domain configuration - complete alignment of all domains with the applied field. Figure 5-3 shows the magnetostriction variation versus normalized magnetization (M/M_s) parallel to the applied field. The initial low-slope region indicates gradual magnetization changes with minimal magnetostriction, attributed to 180° domain wall motion which doesn't affect magnetostriction. As the field increases, 90° wall motion becomes active, reducing domains opposing the field. The steeper slope region in the M/M_s curve reflects rapid approach to saturation, signaling achievement of the ideal single-domain state.

Figure 3.4: Magnetostriction curve as a function of M/M_s .

3.1.3 Domain Structure Dependence on Sample Size

Vortex-like multi-domain configurations in magnetic materials strongly depend on sample size, resulting from competition between short-range exchange energy and long-range magnetostatic energy. Figure 3.5 demonstrates magnetization distribution de-

Figure 3.5: (a) Magnetic domain configuration at the third simulation step for samples with lateral dimensions of: 39 nm (a) 234 nm (b) 468 nm (c)

pendence on lateral dimensions at constant 36 nm thickness. The minimum vortex-stable lateral size is approximately 234 nm. Below this critical size, short-range exchange energy dominates, producing single-domain structures.

3.1.4 Domain Structure Dependence on Magnetostriction Constant

Experimental results show the magnetostriction constant depends on both chemical composition and temperature in iron-gallium alloys. Figure 3.6 displays simulated domain structures with magnetostriction constants $\lambda_{100} = 2.64 \times 10^{-4}$, $\lambda_{111} = 0$, and

Figure 3.6: **(a)** Magnetic domain configuration with magnetostriction constants: $\lambda_{100} = 1.32 \times 10^{-4}$ (a) and $\lambda_{100} = 5.28 \times 10^{-4}$. **(b)**

$$\lambda_{100} = 2/64 \times 10^{-5}, \lambda_{111} = 0.$$

As λ_{100} decreases, [001] domains persist due to reduced elastic energy effects. Adjacent domains must maintain elastic compatibility, requiring equal tangential components of stress-free strain at domain walls. While [110] wall orientations are energetically favorable, [001] domains create unfavorable configurations when interacting with four other [001]-oriented domains.

3.1.5 Domain Structure Dependence on Magnetic Anisotropy Constant

Figure 3.7 shows the magnetic domain configurations considering different values for the magnetic anisotropy constants $K_1 = -2 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$ and $K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4 \text{ J/m}^3$. As observed, the easy magnetic axis in this case is along the [111] direction. In cubic metals, the easy, intermediate, and hard magnetic axes are determined by the magnitude and sign of the magnetic anisotropy constants (Table 5-2). According to this table, in materials where both anisotropy constants are negative, the [111] direction becomes the easy axis since it yields lower anisotropy energy. This demonstrates that the phase field method can predict the effect of magnetic anisotropy constants without requiring any initial assumptions.

Figure 3.7: magnetic domain configurations with different value for the magnetic anisotropy constants $K_1 = -2 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$ and $K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4 \text{ J/m}^3$.

Table 3.2: Magnetic easy, intermediate, and hard axes in cubic crystals

K_2 Range	Crystal Directions		
	Easy	Intermediate	Hard
$[+\infty, -\frac{9}{4}K_1], K_1 > 0$	$\langle 100 \rangle$	$\langle 110 \rangle$	$\langle 111 \rangle$
$[-\frac{9}{4}K_1, -9K_1], K_1 > 0$	$\langle 100 \rangle$	$\langle 111 \rangle$	$\langle 110 \rangle$
$[-9K_1, -\infty], K_1 > 0$	$\langle 111 \rangle$	$\langle 100 \rangle$	$\langle 110 \rangle$
$[-\infty, \frac{9}{4} K_1], K_1 < 0$	$\langle 111 \rangle$	$\langle 110 \rangle$	$\langle 100 \rangle$
$[\frac{9}{4} K_1 , 9 K_1], K_1 < 0$	$\langle 110 \rangle$	$\langle 111 \rangle$	$\langle 100 \rangle$
$[9 K_1 , +\infty], K_1 < 0$	$\langle 110 \rangle$	$\langle 100 \rangle$	$\langle 111 \rangle$

Magnetic Domain Arrangement in Polycrystalline Gallfenol Alloy

Figures 3.8 and 3.9 show the evolution of magnetic domains in the Gallfenol alloy with different anisotropic constants.

Since neighboring grains have different orientations and consequently different easy magnetization axes and anisotropy, each grain essentially behaves as an independent magnet with distinct orientation. The magnetic moments change their direction near grain boundaries to minimize the system's energy. Comparing these two figures re-

Figure 3.8: Magnetic domain temporal evolution of polycrystalline Galfenol under the external applied field in simulation steps of a)1, b) 5, c) 10, d) 15. The anisotropic constants are, $K_1 = 2 \times 10^4 \frac{j}{m^3}$, $K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4 \frac{j}{m^3}$

veals that as the magnetic anisotropy constant increases, the effect of grain boundaries becomes more pronounced. Another noteworthy observation is that the magnetic moment vectors maintain their continuity along grain boundaries, which is essential for minimizing the system's energy.

Figure 3.10 demonstrates the effect of applying an external magnetic field of 8 kA/m in the positive x-direction. Over time, the magnetic moments gradually align with the direction of the applied field.

Figure 3.9: Magnetic domain temporal evolution of polycrystalline Galfenol under the external applied field in simulation steps of a) 1, b) 5, c) 10, d) 15. The anisotropic constants are, $K_1 = 2 \times 10^6 \frac{j}{m^3}$, $K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4 \frac{j}{m^3}$

Figure 3.10: Magnetic domain temporal evolution of polycrystalline Galfenol under the external applied field of $8k_m^A$ in simulation steps of a)1, b) 5, c) 10, d) 15. The anisotropic constants are, $K_1 = 2 \times 10^4 \frac{j}{m^3}$, $K_2 = -4.5 \times 10^4 \frac{j}{m^3}$

Chapter 4

Conclusions

- Cylindrical Sample of $\text{Fe}_{86.32}\text{Ga}_{11.31}\text{Cr}_{2.37}$ Alloy was prepared by vacuum arc remelting (VAR) using a water-cooled copper mold with peripheral cooling and bottom suction.
- The microstructure consisted of small equiaxed grains at the mold contact surface, columnar grains in the radial direction of the cylinder, and equiaxed grains in the central region. Porosity defects caused by insufficient melt feeding were observed in the center, confirming directional solidification. All samples (as-cast and heat-treated) showed single-phase structure, though some secondary phase particles likely from the production process were also observed.
- X-ray diffraction patterns revealed that all three samples had BCC iron single-phase structure. Peak intensity comparison indicated the presence of crystallographic texture. Analysis of peak broadening showed that water-quenching induced residual stresses in the as-cast sample, while air-cooling after annealing released some of these residual stresses.
- The as-cast sample hardness was about 250 Vickers, which remained largely unchanged after heat treatment. Chromium addition was found to increase the hardness and strength of Galfenol.
- Magnetostriction curves versus applied magnetic field were measured using Michelson interferometry. The maximum magnetostriction of 57.9 ppm was observed in the as-cast sample under 25 kA/m applied field. The saturation magnetostriction

decreased to 37.9 ppm in the annealed sample. The minimum magnetostriction of 31.6 ppm was measured in the air-cooled sample.

- Magnetic domain transformations in $\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ga}_{1/87}$ alloy and its magnetostrictive behavior were simulated using phase-field method based on micromagnetism and microelasticity. Simulation results revealed magnetic vortices in the structure whose existence depends on sample size.
- The simulations successfully predicted easy magnetization axes at various magnetic anisotropy constant values without any initial assumptions.
- Magnetic behavior simulation of polycrystalline Galfenol alloy demonstrated grain boundary effects on magnetic moment reorientation when transitioning between adjacent grains. The grain boundary effect increases with higher magnetic anisotropy constants. Results also showed that magnetic domain uniformization under external fields is more difficult in polycrystalline materials compared to single crystals.

Chapter 5

Outlook

- Investigation of magnetostrictive behavior in iron-gallium-chromium alloys with gallium content exceeding 12 atomic percent.
- Study of the effects of hot working processes (such as rolling) and annealing treatments on the physical, mechanical, and magnetic properties of Galfenol to achieve recrystallized structures.
- Exploration of additional alloying elements (e.g., Al, B) and their synergistic effects with chromium.
- Production of Galfenol using alternative rapid solidification methods (e.g., melt spinning) and characterization of its crystallographic texture and magnetostriction.
- Examination of dislocation structures and secondary phases in as-cast samples, and their evolution during heat treatments using transmission electron microscopy (TEM).
- Measurement of magnetic hysteresis loops for both as-cast and heat-treated samples to determine saturation magnetization and coercivity.
- Analysis of ordered structures' influence on magnetostrictive behavior using phase-field modeling.
- Atomic-scale simulation of Galfenol's structure via molecular dynamics or other atomistic methods.

Appendix A

Phase Field Modeling Method

The phase field method is a modeling approach for describing and simulating the temporal evolution of microstructures. Over the past decade, this method has been used to simulate various microstructural phenomena including phase transformations, solidification, dislocation dynamics, grain growth, crack propagation, and coarsening [66].

The fundamental principle involves assigning an order parameter (η) to the microstructure. This abstract parameter can represent various physical quantities such as concentration, crystalline order, magnetic moment, etc.

For example, the solidification process can be modeled using a parameter $\phi(r, t)$ - a function of position (r) and time (t) - that determines the thermodynamic phase of the material:

- $\phi = 1$ represents the solid phase
- $\phi = -1$ represents the liquid phase

As with all thermodynamic systems, the phase at any point $\phi(r, t)$ is determined by the system's free energy.

The order parameter is classified into two categories: conserved and non-conserved [67]. Non-conserved parameters do not need to obey any conservation laws. For example, when a solid transforms to liquid, there is no requirement for mass transfer to or from adjacent regions.

The local concentration of an alloy component represents a conserved parameter, because any increase in concentration at one point must be balanced by an equal

decrease at another point.

In all phase field methods, the temporal evolution of the order parameter η is obtained through variational principles and minimization of the system's free energy $F(\eta, \dots)$. For non-conserved order parameters, this is calculated using the Allen-Cahn or Ginzburg-Landau equations [?]:

$$-\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} = \tau \frac{\delta F}{\delta\phi} = \tau \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial\phi} - \nabla \cdot \frac{\partial F}{\partial(\nabla\phi)} \right) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where τ is the interface relaxation parameter, which depends on the diffusive interface relaxation time.

The temporal evolution of conserved parameters like concentration c is described by the Cahn-Hilliard equation:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(M \nabla \frac{\delta F}{\delta c} \right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Both Allen-Cahn and Cahn-Hilliard models can be solved exactly in special cases. However, in computational materials science applications, advanced numerical methods are typically employed - the equations are discretized in space and then solved numerically [69].

The spatial dependence of variables enables the assignment of heterogeneous structural and compositional phase fields to the microstructure, allowing simulation of transformation kinetics and final morphology. The mechanical assumptions in phase field models treat phase interfaces as diffuse (Figure 3-1). Consequently, they are also referred to as:

- Kinetic phase field models
- Diffuse interface kinetic phase field models [68]

In diffuse interface theory, the total free energy of a heterogeneous microstructure defined by a set of conserved (c_1, c_2, \dots) and non-conserved (ϕ_1, ϕ_2, \dots) field variables is given by:

$$F = \int \left[f(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p) + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i (\nabla c_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_{ij} \nabla_i \phi_k \nabla_j \phi_k \right] d^3r \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$+ \int G(r - r') d^3r d^3r' \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where:

- f is the local free energy density, which is a function of the variables q_i
- α_i are the gradient energy coefficients
- The first volume integral represents the local contribution of short-range chemical interactions to the free energy
- The interface energy is embedded in the gradient energy terms and only has non-zero values at or near interfaces
- The second integral represents a non-local term accounting for long-range interactions such as:
 - Elastic interactions
 - Dipole-dipole electrical interactions
 - Electrostatic interactions

which also depend on the field variables

The main differences between various phase field models arise from how they handle the different contributions to the total free energy.

A.1 Local Free Energy Function

One of the most fundamental components of the phase field method, where materials science plays a significant role, is the definition of the local free energy density function. In many phase field models, particularly for solidification process modeling, double-well potential functions are used:

$$f(\phi) = 4\Delta f \left(-\frac{1}{2}\phi^2 + \frac{1}{4}\phi^4 \right) \quad (3-4) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

In this case, the free energy function has two thermodynamic minima at $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = 1$ (Figure 3-2). The potential barrier height between these two states is determined by the free energy difference.

Another free energy function occasionally used is called the double-obstacle potential:

$$f(\phi) = \Delta f(1 - \phi^2) + I(\phi) \quad (3-5) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where

$$I(\phi) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } |\phi| > 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } |\phi| \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

The advantage of the double-obstacle potential is that, unlike the double-well potential, the field variable value outside the interface rapidly reaches either 1 or -1 [69].

The mentioned forms for local free energy density can only be used for phase transformations (like spinodal decomposition) where both phases have equal energy. However, there exist transformations where at a specific temperature one phase has lower (and thus more stable) energy than the other, while at another temperature the situation reverses.

The relationship describing this behavior can be expressed as:

$$f(\phi, T) = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} \left(-\frac{1}{r}\phi^2 + \frac{1}{r}\phi^3 \right) + \frac{15}{r} \left(\phi - \frac{r}{r}\phi^2 + \frac{1}{r}\phi^5 \right) (T - T_m) \quad (3-6) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where λ is a positive constant and T_m is the melting temperature. This potential is shown at three different temperatures in Figure (3-3).

In most cases, such as when dealing with multiple phases and components, modeling the microstructure requires more than one order parameter. This modeling approach describes the spatiotemporal evolution of multiphase and multicomponent systems. Consider a system containing N phases and K components in a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$. A set of spatiotemporal non-conserved order parameters with values in the interval $[0, 1]$

is introduced and collected in the order parameter vector $\phi = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_N)^T$. The sum of phase field variables at each point must equal unity and represents the local volume fraction of each phase:

$$\sum_{\alpha=1}^N \phi_{\alpha} = 1 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

In this framework, the total free energy of the system is expressed as the sum of free energies of individual phases:

$$f(\phi, \dots) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N h(\phi_{\alpha}) f^{\alpha}(\dots) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where h is an interpolating function that must be continuous, differentiable, and satisfy the conditions:

- $h(0) = 0$
- $h(1) = 1$

A.2 Elastic Free Energy

In all phase transformations, elastic strain energy exists unless the volume change equals zero [70]. Zero elastic energy can only be achieved if we assume that adding or removing units of the α phase causes the cavity to expand or contract sufficiently so that the transformed phase fits precisely into the cavity without stress. In this case, no surface forces exist and both α and β phases remain stress-free, though some surface rearrangements may occur to minimize surface energy. The number of atoms in the region that ultimately becomes β phase does not remain constant, and the formation of a stress-free β phase depends on whether diffusion or plastic flow can compensate for the changes in shape and size.

At sufficiently high temperatures, the flow rate in a crystal is adequate to relieve internal stresses, making the elastic energy negligible at these temperatures. At low temperatures, diffusion rates become insufficient, resulting in significant residual elastic energy. When the strain energy from transformation is large, nucleation typically occurs at defects such as grain boundaries since the required transformation work

is significantly reduced in these regions. The elastic free energy f_{el} is given by the interpolated sum of elastic energies from each phase α , expressed as:

$$f_{el}^\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_\alpha^*)\mathbf{C}^\alpha(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_\alpha^*) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where \mathbf{C}^α represents the elastic stiffness tensor and ε_α^* denotes the transformation strain in phase α . For the complete system, the elastic free energy becomes:

$$f_{el} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N h(\varphi_\alpha) f_{el}^\alpha \quad (\text{3-10}) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

A.3 Numerical Methods for Phase Field Equations

Phase field modeling of microstructural evolution involves solving the kinetic equations A.1, and A.2 . Most phase field simulations employ second-order finite difference methods on uniform grids with forward time stepping. The time step must be chosen sufficiently small to obtain stable numerical solutions. For periodic boundary conditions, the semi-implicit Fourier spectral method is frequently used, which transforms integro-differential equations into algebraic equations in reciprocal space, allowing for larger time steps. However, a limitation of this approach is that while the spatial discretization While offering periodic accuracy in space, the method still maintains only first-order accuracy in time, making numerical stability problematic.

Recently, more efficient and accurate semi-implicit Fourier-spectral algorithms have been employed to solve phase field relations. These algorithms are significantly more precise than conventional forward methods. This approach can also be applied under Dirichlet, Neumann, or mixed boundary conditions when combined with Chebyshev-spectral or Legendre-spectral methods. However, since spectral methods typically utilize uniform grid spacing, analyzing extremely narrow interfaces remains challenging. In such cases, it is preferable to use an adaptive spectral method [69].

Appendix B

Gauss-Seidel Projection Method for Micromagnetic Phenomena Simulation

The magnetic domain structures are obtained by numerically solving the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation using the Gauss-Seidel projection method [?]. The Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation is transformed using dimensionless variables:

$$\mathbf{M} = M_s \mathbf{m} \tag{B.1}$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{eff} = M_s \mathbf{h}_{eff} \tag{B.2}$$

$$t = \frac{1 + \alpha^2}{\gamma M_s} \tau \tag{B.3}$$

The equation becomes:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}}{\partial \tau} = -\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{h}_{eff} - \alpha \mathbf{m} \times (\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{h}_{eff}) \tag{B.4}$$

The effective magnetic field can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{h}_{eff} &= \frac{1}{M_s} (\mathbf{H}_{eff} + \mathbf{H}_{eff}) = \frac{1}{M_s} \left[\left(-\frac{\partial E_{exch}}{\partial \mathbf{M}} \right) + \left(-\frac{\partial E'}{\mu_0 \partial \mathbf{M}} \right) \right] \\ &= A^* \Delta \mathbf{m} + \frac{1}{M_s} \left(-\frac{\partial E'}{\mu_0 \partial \mathbf{M}} \right) = A^* \Delta \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{h}[\mathbf{m}] \quad (\text{B.5})\end{aligned}$$

where E is the total free energy excluding the exchange energy. A^* is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{m} \times (A^* \Delta \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{h}[\mathbf{m}]) - \alpha \mathbf{m} \times (\mathbf{m} \times (A^* \Delta \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{h}[\mathbf{m}])) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where A^* represents the cell size used in the model.

Equation B.6 is solved in three steps:

Step 1:

$$\mathbf{g}_i^n = (1 - A^* \Delta t \Delta)^{-1} (\mathbf{m}_i^n + \Delta t \mathbf{h}_i[\mathbf{m}^n]) \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\mathbf{g}_i^* = (1 - A^* \Delta t \Delta)^{-1} (\mathbf{m}_i^* + \Delta t \mathbf{h}_i[\mathbf{m}^n]) \quad (\text{2-5}) \quad (\text{B.8})$$

For $i = 1, 2, 3$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_1^* \\ m_2^* \\ m_3^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1^n + (g_2^n m_3^n - g_3^n m_2^n) \\ m_2^n + (g_3^n m_1^n - g_1^n m_3^n) \\ m_3^n + (g_1^n m_2^n - g_2^n m_1^n) \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{2-6}) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Step 2:

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_1^{**} \\ m_2^{**} \\ m_3^{**} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1^* + \alpha \Delta t (A^* \Delta m_1^{**} + h_1[\mathbf{m}^*]) \\ m_2^* + \alpha \Delta t (A^* \Delta m_2^{**} + h_2[\mathbf{m}^*]) \\ m_3^* + \alpha \Delta t (A^* \Delta m_3^{**} + h_3[\mathbf{m}^*]) \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Step 3:

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_1^{n+1} \\ m_2^{n+1} \\ m_3^{n+1} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{m}^{**}|} \begin{pmatrix} m_1^{**} \\ m_2^{**} \\ m_3^{**} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{2-8}) \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Equations B.7 and B.10 are solved using Fourier transform.

Appendix C

Three-Dimensional Grain Growth Simulation

Based on the polycrystalline grain growth model proposed by Krill and Chen [?], a polycrystalline microstructure is described by a set of continuous phase field parameters $\{\eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t)\}$ defined at position \mathbf{r} and time t . The thermodynamic simulation algorithm is formulated to minimize the system's free energy when:

- Only one phase field parameter equals 1 within each grain
- All other parameters equal 0

Thus, each grain's orientation is specified by the index q of the phase field parameter equal to 1, while grain boundaries take values between 0 and 1. This model, like most diffusion-controlled growth processes, is based on the Allen-Cahn equation. The total free energy of a polycrystal is expressed as:

$$F(t) = \int \left[f_\eta(\eta_1(\mathbf{r}, t), \eta_2(\mathbf{r}, t), \dots, \eta_Q(\mathbf{r}, t)) + \sum_{q=1}^Q \frac{\kappa_q}{2} (\nabla \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t))^2 \right] d\mathbf{r} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where κ_q are positive constants and f_η is the local free energy density, defined as:

$$f_\eta(\{\eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t)\}) = -\frac{\alpha}{2} \sum_{q=1}^Q \eta_q^2(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{\beta}{4} \left(\sum_{q=1}^Q \eta_q^2(\mathbf{r}, t) \right)^2 \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$+ \left(\gamma - \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{s>q}^Q \eta_q^2(\mathbf{r}, t) \eta_s^2(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

where α , β , and γ are constants.

The quadratic dependence of F on the gradient of each phase field parameter introduces an energetic penalty for grain boundaries, creating a thermodynamic driving force for grain boundary elimination (i.e., grain growth):

The temporal evolution of phase field parameters follows the Ginzburg-Landau equation:

$$\frac{\partial \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = -L_q \frac{\delta F(t)}{\delta \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t)} = -L_q \left(-\alpha \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t) + \beta \eta_q^3(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$+ 2\gamma \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t) \sum_{\substack{s=1 \\ s \neq q}}^Q \eta_s^2(\mathbf{r}, t) - \kappa_q \nabla^2 \eta_q(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where:

- L_q are kinetic coefficients related to grain boundary mobility
- α , β , γ are thermodynamic parameters
- κ_q is the gradient energy coefficient

The finite difference method is employed for numerical solution of equation (3-7).

References

- [1] Cullity, Bernard Dennis, and Chad D. Graham. *Introduction to magnetic materials*. John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- [2] Restorff, J. B., M. Wun-Fogle, K. B. Hathaway, A. E. Clark, Thomas A. Lograsso, and G. Petculescu. “Tetragonal magnetostriction and magnetoelastic coupling in Fe-Al, Fe-Ga, Fe-Ge, Fe-Si, Fe-Ga-Al, and Fe-Ga-Ge alloys.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 111.2 (2012): 023905.
- [3] Clark, Arthur E., et al. “Magnetostrictive properties of body-centered cubic Fe-Ga and Fe-Ga-Al alloys.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 36.5 (2000): 3238–3240.
- [4] Hall, R. C. “Single-Crystal Magnetic Anisotropy and Magnetostriction Studies in Iron-Base Alloys.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 31.6 (1960): 1037–1038.
- [5] Li, J. H., et al. “Ductility, texture and large magnetostriction of Fe–Ga-based sheets.” *Scripta Materialia* 63.2 (2010): 246–249.
- [6] Summers, E. M., T. A. Lograsso, and M. Wun-Fogle. “Magnetostriction of binary and ternary Fe–Ga alloys.” *Journal of Materials Science* 42.23 (2007): 9582–9594.
- [7] Kellogg, R. A. *Development and modeling of iron–gallium alloys*. PhD Thesis, Engineering Mechanics, Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa, 2003. Available online at: http://www.aero.umd.edu/~aflatau/TechPubs/Kellogg_2003_Dissertation.pdf
- [8] Hatchard, T. D., George, A. E., Farrell, S. P., Steinitz, M. O., Adams, C. P., Cormier, M., & Dunlap, R. A. “Production and characterization of $\langle 100 \rangle$ textured magnetostrictive Fe–Ga rods.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 494.1 (2010): 420–425.
- [9] Na, Suok-Min, and Alison B. Flatau. “Single grain growth and large magnetostriction in secondarily recrystallized Fe-Ga thin sheet with sharp Goss (011)[100] orientation.” *Scripta Materialia* 66.5 (2012): 307–310.
- [10] Farrell, S. P., Quigley, P. E., Avery, K. J., Hatchard, T. D., Flynn, S. E., & Dunlap, R. A. “Development of $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystallographic texture in magnetostrictive Fe-Ga wires using a modified Taylor wire method.” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* 42.13 (2009): 135005.
- [11] Cheng, S. F., Das, B. N., Wun-Fogle, M., Lubitz, P., & Clark, A. E. “Structure

- of melt-spun Fe-Ga-based magnetostrictive alloys.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetism* 38.5 (2002): 2838–2840.
- [12] Takahashi, T., Hashimoto, K., Okazaki, T., Furuya, Y., Kubota, T., & Saito, C. “Characterization of magnetostrictive Fe-Ga-based alloys fabricated by rapid solidification.” *Scripta Materialia* 60.10 (2009): 847–849.
- [13] Zhang, M. C., Gao, X. X., Jiang, H. L., Qiao, Y., & Zhou, S. Z. “Effect of Ga content on the magnetostriction and microstructure of Fe-Ga ribbons.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 431.1 (2007): 42–44.
- [14] Sun, L., Zhang, M., Gao, X. X., Qiao, Y., & Zhu, J. “Effect of quenching on magnetostriction and microstructure of melt-spun Fe₈₃Ga₁₇ alloy.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 463.1 (2008): 6–9.
- [15] Srisukhumbowornchai, N., and S. Guruswamy. “Large magnetostriction in directionally solidified FeGa and FeGaAl alloys.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 90.11 (2001): 5680–5688.
- [16] Mungsantisuk, P., Corson, R., & Guruswamy, S. “Study on the Structure and Magnetostriction Properties of Fe_{81-y}Co_yGa₁₉ thin films.” In: Chandra, D., Bautista, R. G., & Schlapbach, L. (eds.) *Advanced Materials for Energy Conversion II*. TMS, p. 275, 2004.
- [17] Gao, X., Li, J., Zhu, J., Li, J., & Zhang, M. “Effect of B and Cr on Mechanical Properties and Magnetostriction of Iron-Gallium Alloy.” *Materials Transactions* 50.8 (2009): 1959–1963.
- [18] Brown, William Fuller. *Micromagnetics*. No. 18. New York: Interscience Publishers, 1963.
- [19] Zhang, J. X., & Chen, L. Q. “Phase-field microelasticity theory and micromagnetic simulations of domain structures in giant magnetostrictive materials.” *Acta Materialia* 53.9 (2005): 2845–2855.
- [20] Spaldin, Nicola A. *Magnetic Materials: Fundamentals and Applications*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [21] O’Handley, Robert C. *Modern Magnetic Materials: Principles and Applications*. Vol. 830622677. New York: Wiley, 2000.

- [22] Bobbio, Scipione. “Electrodynamics of Materials.” *Forces, Stresses, and Energies in Solids and Fluids* (2000).
- [23] Lee, Eric W. “Magnetostriction and Magnetomechanical Effects.” *Reports on Progress in Physics* 18.1 (1955): 184.
- [24] Grossinger, R., Sassik, H., Holzer, D., & Pillmayr, N. *Accurate Measurement of the Magnetostriction of Soft Magnetic Materials*. na, 2006.
- [25] Ramanathan, Meenakshisundaram. *Effect of Hydrogen and Magnetic Field on the Mechanical Behavior of Magnetostrictive Iron-Gallium Alloys*. PhD Dissertation, University of Utah, 2012.
- [26] Williams, Wyn, and David J. Dunlop. “Three-Dimensional Micromagnetic Modelling of Ferromagnetic Domain Structure.” *Nature* 337.6208 (1989): 634–637.
- [27] Williams, W., and T. M. Wright. “High-Resolution Micromagnetic Models of Fine Grains of Magnetite.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 103.B12 (1998): 30537–30550.
- [28] Cowburn, R. P., and M. E. Welland. “Micromagnetics of the Single-Domain State of Square Ferromagnetic Nanostructures.” *Physical Review B* 58.14 (1998): 9217.
- [29] Fidler, Josef, and Thomas Schrefl. “Micromagnetic Modelling - The Current State of the Art.” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* 33.15 (2000): R135.
- [30] Hertel, Riccardo, and H. Kronmüller. “Adaptive Finite Element Mesh Refinement Techniques in Three-Dimensional Micromagnetic Modeling.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 34.6 (1998): 3922–3930.
- [31] Schrefl, T., Fidler, J., Kirk, K. J., & Chapman, J. N. “A Higher Order FEM-BEM Method for the Calculation of Domain Processes in Magnetic Nano-Elements.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 33.5 (1997): 4182–4184.
- [32] Schrefl, Thomas, and Josef Fidler. “Finite Element Modeling of Nanocomposite Magnets.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 35.5 (1999): 3223–3228.
- [33] Fischbacher, T., Franchin, M., Bordignon, G., & Fangohr, H. “A Systematic Approach to Multiphysics Extensions of Finite-Element-Based micromagnetic simulations: Nmag. Magnetics, IEEE Transactions on, 43(6), 2896 2898.
- [34] Zhu, B., Lo, C. C. H., Lee, S. J., & Jiles, D. C. “Micromagnetic Modeling of the

- Effects of Stress on Magnetic Properties.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 89.11 (2001): 7009–7011.
- [35] Liu, Z. H.; Liu, G. D.; Zhang, M.; Wu, G. H.; Meng, F. B.; Liu, H. Y.; Yan, L. Q.; Qu, J. P.; Li, Y. X. “Large Magnetostriction in $\text{Fe}_{100-x}\text{Al}_x$ ($15 \leq x \leq 30$) Melt-Spun Ribbons.” *Applied Physics Letters* 85.10 (2004): 1751–1753.
- [36] Wuttig, Manfred, Liyang Dai, and James Cullen. “Elasticity and Magnetoelasticity of Fe-Ga Solid Solutions.” *Applied Physics Letters* 80.7 (2002): 1135–1137.
- [37] Clark, A. E., Wun-Fogle, M., Restorff, J. B., Lograsso, T. A., & Cullen, J. R. “Effect of Quenching on the Magnetostriction of $\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x$ ($0.13 < x < 0.21$).” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 37.4 (2001): 2678–2680.
- [38] Ikeda, O., Kainuma, R., Ohnuma, I., Fukamichi, K., and Ishida, K. “Phase Equilibria and Stability of Ordered BCC Phases in the Fe-Rich Portion of the Fe-Ga System.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 347.1 (2002): 198–205.
- [39] Lograsso, T. A., Ross, A. R., Schlagel, D. L., Clark, A. E., & Wun-Fogle, M. “Structural Transformations in Quenched Fe-Ga Alloys.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 350.1 (2003): 95–101.
- [40] ASM Handbook. *Volume 3: Alloy Phase Diagrams*. ASM International, 1992.
- [48] Cao, H., Gehring, P. M., Devreugd, C. P., Rodriguez-Rivera, J. A., Li, J., & Viehland, D. “Role of Nanoscale Precipitates on the Enhanced Magnetostriction of Heat-Treated Galfenol ($\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x$) Alloys.” *Physical Review Letters* 102.12 (2009): 127201.
- [49] Ruffoni, M. P., and S. Pascarelli. “Measurement of Intrinsic Magnetostriction in Fe-Ga Alloys.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 45.10 (2009): 4136–4141.
- [50] Du, Y., Huang, M., Chang, S., Schlagel, D. L., Lograsso, T. A., & McQueeney, R. J. “Relation between Ga Ordering and Magnetostriction of Fe-Ga Alloys Studied by X-ray Diffuse Scattering.” *Physical Review B* 81.5 (2010): 054432.
- [51] Wang, H., Zhang, Y. N., Wu, R. Q., Sun, L. Z., Xu, D. S., & Zhang, Z. D. “Understanding Strong Magnetostriction in $\text{Fe}_{100-x}\text{Ga}_x$ Alloys.” *Scientific Reports* 3 (2013).
- [52] Yuan, C., Li, J., Bao, X., & Gao, X. “Influence of Annealing Process on Texture

Evolution and Magnetostriction in Rolled Fe-Ga Based Alloys.” *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 362 (2014): 154–158.

[53] Boesenberg, A. J., Restorff, J. B., Wun-Fogle, M., Salisbury, H., & Summers, E. “Texture Development in Galfenol Wire.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 113.17 (2013): 17A909.

[54] Turtelli, R. S., Pascarelli, S., Ruffoni, M., Grossinger, R., & Eisenmenger-Sittner, C. “Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) and X-ray Absorption Near-Edge Structure (XANES) Study of Melt-Spun Fe₈₅Ga₁₅ Ribbons.” *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 320.20 (2008): e578–e582.

[55] Bormio-Nunes, C., Sato Turtelli, R., Grossinger, R., Muller, H., & Sassik, H. “Magnetostriction of Melt-Spun Fe₈₅Ga₁₅, Fe₇₈Ni₇Ga₁₅ and Fe₇₈Co₇Ga₁₅ Stacked ribbon samples.” *Journal of magnetism and magnetic materials* 322.9-12 (2010): 1605-1608.

[56] Hu, Y., Ding, Y., Zhang, Y., Wang, G., & Zhou, Z. “Magnetostriction and Structural Characterization of Fe-Ga Bulk Alloy Prepared by Copper Mold Casting.” *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China* 22.9 (2012): 2146–2152.

[57] Restorff, J. B., Wun-Fogle, M., Clark, A. E., Lograsso, T. A., Ross, A. R., & Schlagel, D. L. “Magnetostriction of Ternary Fe-Ga-X Alloys (X = Ni, Mo, Sn, Al).” *Journal of Applied Physics* 91.10 (2002): 8225–8227.

[58] Bormio-Nunes, C., Sato Turtelli, R., Muller, H., Grossinger, R., Sassik, H., & Tirelli, M. A. “Magnetostriction and Structural Characterization of Fe-Ga-X (X = Co, Ni, Al) Mold-Cast Bulk.” *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 290 (2005): 820–822.

[59] Choudhury, S., Li, Y. L., Krill III, C. E., & Chen, L. Q. “Phase-Field Simulation of Polarization Switching and Domain Evolution in Ferroelectric Polycrystals.” *Acta Materialia* 53.20 (2005): 5313–5321.

[60] Porter, D. A., and K. E. Easterling. *Phase Transformations in Metals and Alloys*. Nelson Thornes Ltd., 2001.

[61] Reed-Hill, Robert E., and Reza Abbaschian. *Physical Metallurgy Principles*. PWS-Kent, Boston, 1994.

- [62] Kriegisch, M.; Groessinger, R.; Grijalva, C.; Muhammad, A.; Kneidinger, F.; Mehboob, N.; Kubel, F.; & Turtelli, R. S. “Magnetic Properties of Highly Textured $\text{Fe}_{85}\text{Ga}_{15}$.” *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 50.6 (2014): 1–5.
- [63] Gu, M., Zhou, J., & Li, J. “Microstructural Evolution of Undercooled $\text{Fe}_{83}\text{Ga}_{17}$ Magnetostrictive Alloys.” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 441.1 (2007): 81–84.
- [64] Jie, Z., Fu-Ling, P., Mei-Ling, F., Ji-Heng, L., Xue-Xu, G., & Rong-Hai, Y. “Short Range Order Transformation and Magnetostriction of $\text{Fe}_{83}\text{Ga}_{17}$ Ribbons.” *Chinese Physics B* 20.5 (2011): 057504.
- [65] Summers, E. M., Lograsso, T. A., Snodgrass, J. D., & Slaughter, J. C. “Magnetic and Mechanical Properties of Polycrystalline Galfenol.” In *Smart Structures and Materials* (pp. 448–459). International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2004.
- [66] Moelans, N., Blanpain, B., & Wollants, P. “An Introduction to Phase-Field Modeling of Microstructure Evolution.” *CALPHAD* 32.2 (2008): 268–294.
- [67] LeSar, R. *Introduction to Computational Materials Science: Fundamentals to Applications*. Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- [68] Raabe, D. *Computational Materials Science: The Simulation of Materials Microstructures and Properties*. Wiley, 1998.
- [69] Chen, L.-Q. “Phase-Field Models for Microstructure Evolution.” *Annual Review of Materials Research* 32.1 (2002): 113–140.
- [70] Christian, J. W. *The Theory of Transformations in Metals and Alloys*. Pergamon, Oxford, 2002.
- [71] Wang, X.-P., & Garcia-Cervera, C. J. “A Gauss-Seidel Projection Method for Micromagnetics Simulations.” *Journal of Computational Physics* 171.1 (2001): 357–372.
- [72] Krill Iii, C. E., and L-Q. Chen. ”Computer simulation of 3-D grain growth using a phase-field model.” *Acta Materialia* 50.12 (2002): 3059-3075.